

Prime gapology

Adolf Cusmariu

Email: adolcus@gmail.com

Let's get the primes up to 10 billion from

```
pr=primes(1.e10);
```

There are 455,052,510 odd primes here; get the spacing between consecutive primes via

```
gap=diff(pr);
```

and the commands

```
unq=unique(gap);,len=length(unq)
```

show there are 166 unique spacings, ranging in value from 2 (for twins) to 354. Kurtosis of the spacings string is 8.241.

To get the occurrence string (i.e., histogram) do

```
for k=1:len,occ(k)=length(find(gap==unq(k)));,end
```

This histogram is (partially) bar-plotted below; `bar(unq,occ)` is the command.

It is interesting that **6** (`occ(3)`) is the most frequent spacing here, and even at lower ranges; see bar plots below (respective `occ` only), derived from odd primes up to 1, 10, 100 million and 1 billion.

Since $1 + \text{sum}(\text{occ}) = 455,052,510 = \#$ of odd primes here, every odd prime belongs uniquely to some gap family, whether composed of 2 (twins), 4, 6, ...; thus we have a complete decomposition of odd primes into disjoint pairs according to gap widths.

As a verification, there are 99,99,999,998 integers here, excluding 1 and 2; and the greatest prime is 9,999,999,967. Hence the vector inner product (occ,unq) yields correctly

$$1 + (\text{occ}, \text{unq}) = 9,999,999,965$$

the total number of integers, including the prime 'endpoints'. As a further check, to count the number of integers between the prime gaps, let

$$\text{unq1} = \text{unq} - 1$$

The inner product (occ,unq1) yields the total integer count in between the prime gaps:

$$(\text{occ}, \text{unq1}) = 9,544,947,455$$

When this is added to the total number of odd primes $1 + \text{sum}(\text{occ}) = 455,052,510$, the result is

$$(\text{occ}, \text{unq1}) + 1 + \text{sum}(\text{occ}) = 1 + (\text{occ}, \text{unq})$$

as expected.

Now, when plotted in log scale, the occurrence string $\log(\text{occ})$ appears an AM-FM sinusoid superimposed on a downward slope (next page); symbolically then, $\text{occ} \sim \exp(\text{amfm})\exp(\text{lin})$.

More precisely, a linear fit of $\log(\text{occ})$ follows from the command

```
fit=polyfit(1:len,log(occ),1);
```

The fit line with the resulting coefficients is

```
lin=polyval(fit,1:len);
```

The residual

$$\text{res} = \log(\text{occ}) - \text{lin}$$

is plotted below.

Spectral analysis of this sinusoid yielded a period of 3 samples. Thus $\text{oc3} \equiv \text{occ}(3k)$, $k=1, 2, \dots, \text{len}$, is (essentially) periodic here, with an exponentially decaying amplitude. A partial bar chart of oc3 is shown below

A 4th order polynomial (pol3) fit through log(oc3) yielded a reasonably small residual res3 \equiv log(oc3) - pol3; see below.

Even if neglecting this residual, the simple estimate exp(pol3) compares favorably with oc3.

Finally, let's get a counter for the most frequently occurring prime gap of **6** (occ(3))

$$\pi_6(n) = \#\{\text{primes } p \leq n: p(n+1)-p(n)=6\}$$

Estimation for primes from 1 billion to 10 billion in 500 million increments yielded the counter

$$\pi_6(n) \approx n/\log(n)^\alpha \quad \text{where } \alpha = 1.69308$$

The percent fractional error is plotted below; it was .00071553% at 10 billion primes.

